

Flow rate fractal dimension for characterizing Shajara reservoirs of the Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Flow rate fractal dimension was employed to describe in details the internal pore geometrical features of real outcrop sandstone samples of the Shajara reservoirs of the Shajara Formation, Saudi Arabia. The flow rate was derived from relationship among pore radius, differential pressure, fluid viscosity, and capillary length. The pore radius was obtained from capillary pressure measured by mercury injection. However, the capillary length was calculated from correlation between surface tension, contact angle, fluid density, gravitational acceleration, and pore radius. The flow rate fractal dimension was achieved from the slope = $3-D_f$ of the ratio of logarithm flow rate at specific saturation to maximum flow rate versus logarithm wetting phase saturation. Through combing field observations and acquired results of fractal dimension, the Shajara reservoirs of the Shajara Formation were divided here into three units. These stratigraphic units from bottom to top are: lower Shajara flow Rate Fractal Dimension Unit, Middle Shajara Flow Rate Fractal Dimension Unit, and Upper Shajara flow Rate Fractal Dimension unit. The three reservoir units were also confirmed by capillary pressure fractal dimension As conclusive evidence the flow rate fractal dimension was found to increase with increasing permeability and pore connectivity.

Introduction

The wetting phase saturation can be described as function of capillary pressure and fractal dimension was demonstrated by [1]. The Purcell model was found to be the best fit to the experimental data of the wetting phase relative permeability for the cases as long as the measured capillary pressure curve had the same residual saturation as the relative permeability curve was described by [2]. A theoretical model to correlate capillary pressure and resistivity index based on the fractal scaling theory was reported by [3]. The fractal dimension resulting from longer transverse NMR relaxation times and lower capillary pressure reflects the volume dimension of larger pores was described by [4]. The fractal dimension derived from the short NMR relaxation times is similar to the fractal dimension of the internal surface was described by [4]. The fractal dimensions can be used to represent the complexity degree and heterogeneity of pore structure, and the coexistence of dissolution pores and large intergranular pores of Donghetang sandstones contributes to a heterogeneous pore throat distribution and a high value of fractal dimension was reported

by [5]. The relationship among capillary pressure (PC), nuclear magnetic transverse relaxation time (T2) and resistivity index (I) was studied by [6]. An increase of bubble pressure fractal dimension and pressure head fractal dimension and decreasing pore size distribution index and fitting parameters m^n due to possibility of having interconnected channels was confirmed by [7]. An increase of fractal dimension with increasing arithmetic, geometric relaxation time of induced polarization, permeability and grain size was investigated by [8,9,10]. An increase of seismo electric and resistivity fractal dimensions with increasing permeability and grain size was described by [11,12].

Materials and Methods

Sandstone samples were collected from the surface type section of the Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation, latitude 26 52 17.4, longitude 43 36 18. (Figure1). Porosity was measured on collected samples using mercury intrusion Porosimetry and permeability was derived from capillary pressure data. The purpose of this paper is to obtain flow rate fractal dimension

and to confirm it by capillary pressure fractal dimension. The fractal dimension of the first procedure is determined from the positive slope of the plot of logarithm of the ratio of flow rate to maximum flow rate versus log wetting phase saturation (logSw). Whereas the fractal dimension of the second procedure is determined from the negative slope of the plot of logarithm of log capillary pressure (log (Pc) versus logarithm of wetting phase saturation (log Sw).

The flow rate fractal dimension can be scaled as

$$Sw = \left[\frac{Q^{0.25}}{Q_{max}^{0.25}} \right]^{3-Df} = \left[\frac{Q^{\frac{1}{4}}}{Q_{max}^{\frac{1}{4}}} \right]^{3-Df} \quad 1$$

Where Sw the water saturation, Q the flow rate in cubic meter / second; Qmax the maximum flow rate in cubic meter / second, Df the fractal dimension.

Equation 1 can be proofed from

$$Q = \frac{[\pi * r^4 * \Delta p]}{[8 * \mu * L]} \quad 2$$

Where Q the flow rate in cubic meter / second, r the pore throat radius in meter, Δp the differential pressure in pascal, μ the fluid viscosity in pascal* second; L the capillary length in meter.

Equation 2 after rearrange will become

$$r^4 = \frac{[8 * Q * \mu * L]}{[\pi * \Delta p]} \quad 3$$

The maximum flow rate can be scaled as

$$r_{max}^4 = \frac{[8 * Q_{max} * \mu * L]}{[\pi * \Delta p]} \quad 4$$

Divide equation 3 by equation 4

$$\frac{r^4}{r_{max}^4} = \frac{[8 * Q * \mu * L]}{[\pi * \Delta p]} \div \frac{[8 * Q_{max} * \mu * L]}{[\pi * \Delta p]} \quad 5$$

Equation 5 after simplification will become

$$\frac{r^4}{r_{max}^4} = \left[\frac{Q}{Q_{max}} \right] \quad 6$$

Take the fourth root of equation 6

$$\sqrt[4]{\left[\frac{r^4}{r_{max}^4} \right]} = \sqrt[4]{\left[\frac{Q}{Q_{max}} \right]} \quad 7$$

Equation 7 after simplification will become

$$\left[\frac{r}{r_{max}} \right] = \left[\frac{Q^{0.25}}{Q_{max}^{0.25}} \right] \quad 8$$

Take the logarithm of equation 8

$$\text{Log} \left[\frac{r}{r_{max}} \right] = \text{Log} \left[\frac{Q^{0.25}}{Q_{max}^{0.25}} \right] \quad 9$$

$$\text{But ; Log} \left[\frac{r}{r_{max}} \right] = \text{Log} \frac{Sw}{[3 - Df]} \quad 10$$

Where Sw the water saturation, Df the fractal dimension
Insert equation 10 into equation 9

$$\text{Log} \frac{Sw}{[3 - Df]} = \text{Log} \left[\frac{Q^{0.25}}{Q_{max}^{0.25}} \right] \quad 11$$

If we remove the logarithm from equation 11

$$Sw = \left[\frac{Q^{0.25}}{Q_{max}^{0.25}} \right]^{3-Df} = \left[\frac{Q^{\frac{1}{4}}}{Q_{max}^{\frac{1}{4}}} \right]^{3-Df} \quad 12$$

Equation 12 the proof of equation 1 which relates the water saturation Sw, The flow rate Q, the maximum flow rate Qmax, the fractal dimension Df.

The capillary can be scaled as

$$\text{Log Sw} = [Df - 3] * Pc + \text{constant} \quad 13$$

Where Sw the water saturation, Pc the capillary pressure, and Df the fractal dimension

Result and discussion

Based on field observation the Shajara Reservoirs of the Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation were divided here into three units as described in Figure1. These units from bottom to top are: Lower Shajara Reservoir, Middle Shajara reservoir, and Upper Shajara Reservoir. Their acquired results of the number of moles fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension are displayed in Table 1. Based on the attained results it was found that the flow rate fractal dimension is equal to the capillary pressure fractal dimension. The maximum value of the fractal dimension was found to be 2.7872 assigned to sample SJ13 from the Upper Shajara Reservoir as verified in Table 1. Whereas the minimum value of the fractal dimension 2.4379 was reported from sample SJ3 from the Lower Shajara reservoir as displayed in Table1. The flow rate fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension were observed to increase with increasing permeability as proofed in Table1 owing to the possibility of having interconnected channels.

The Lower Shajara reservoir was denoted by six sandstone samples (Figure 1), four of which label as SJ1, SJ2, SJ3 and SJ4 were selected for capillary pressure measurement as confirmed in Table1. Their positive slopes of the first procedure log of the ratio of flow rate to maximum flow rate

versus log wetting phase saturation (S_w) and negative slopes of the second procedure log capillary pressure (P_c) versus log wetting phase saturation (S_w) are delineated in Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4, and Figure 5. Their flow rate fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension values are shown in Table 1. As we proceed from sample SJ2 to SJ3 a pronounced reduction in permeability due to compaction was reported from

1955 md to 56 md which reflects decrease in flow rate fractal dimension from 2.7748 to 2.4379 as specified in table 1. Again, an increase in grain size and permeability was verified from sample SJ4 whose flow rate fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension was found to be 2.6843 as described in (Table 1).

AGE	Fm.	Mbr.	unit	LITHO-LOGY	DESCRIPTION	
Late Permian	Khuff Formation	Hugayf Member			Limestone : Cream, dense, burrowed, thickness 6.56' Sub-Khuff unconformity.	
Late Carboniferous - Permian	Shajara Formation	Upper Shajara Member	Upper Shajara		Mudstone : Yellow, thickness 17.7'	
			SJ15 ▲	Sandstone : Light brown, cross-bedded, coarse-grained, poorly sorted, porous, friable, thickness 6.5'		
			SJ12 ▲	Sandstone : Yellow, medium-grained, very coarse-grained, poorly sorted, moderately sorted, porous, friable, thickness 13.1'		
			SJ11 ▲	Mudstone : Yellow-green, thickness 11.8'		
		Middle Shajara Member	Middle Shajara		Mudstone : Yellow, thickness 1.3' Mudstone : Brown, thickness 4.5'	
			SJ10 ▲	Sandstone : Light brown, medium-grained, moderately sorted, porous, friable, thickness 3.6'		
			SJ9 ▲	Sandstone : Yellow, medium-grained, moderately well sorted, porous, friable, thickness 0.9'		
			SJ8 ▲	Sandstone : Red, coarse-grained, medium-grained, moderately well sorted, porous, friable, thickness 13.4'		
		Lower Shajara Member	Lower Shajara		SJ7 ▲	Sandstone : White with yellow spots, fine-grained, hard, thickness 2.6'
			SJ6 ▲	Sandstone : Limestone, thickness 1.3'		
			SJ5 ▲	Sandstone : White, coarse-grained, very poorly sorted, thickness 4.5'		
			SJ4 ▲	Sandstone : White-pink, poorly sorted, thickness 1.6'		
			SJ3 ▲	Sandstone : Yellow, medium-grained, well sorted, porous, friable, thickness 3.9'		
Early Devonian	Duwali Formation			Sandstone : Red, medium-grained, moderately well sorted, porous, friable, thickness 11.8' Sub-Umayyah unconformity. Sandstone : White, fine-grained.		

Figure 1: Surface type section of the Shajara reservoirs of the Permo-Carboniferous Shajara Formation at latitude 26 52 17.4, longitude 43 36 18.

Figure 2: Log ($Q^{0.25}/Q_{max}^{0.25}$) & log p_c versus log S_w for sample Sj1.

Figure 4: Log ($Q^{0.25}/Q_{max}^{0.25}$) & log p_c versus log S_w for sample Sj3

Figure 3: Log ($Q^{0.25}/Q_{max}^{0.25}$) & log p_c versus log S_w for sample Sj2.

Figure 5: Log ($Q^{0.25}/Q_{max}^{0.25}$) & log p_c versus log S_w for sample Sj4.

In contrast, the Middle Shajara reservoir which is separated from the Lower Shajara reservoir by an unconformity surface as shown in Figure 1. It was designated by four samples (Figure 1), three of which named as SJ7, SJ8, and SJ9 as illustrated in Table 1. Their positive slopes of the first procedure and negative slopes of the second procedure are shown in Figure 6, Figure 7 and Figure 8 and Table 1. Additionally, their flow rate fractal dimensions and capillary pressure fractal dimensions show similarities as delineated in Table 1. Their fractal dimensions are higher than those of samples SJ3 and SJ4 from the Lower Shajara Reservoir due to an increase in their permeability as explained in (Table 1).

Figure 8: $\text{Log} (Q^{0.25}/Q_{\text{max}}^{0.25})$ & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ9.

On the other hand, the Upper Shajara reservoir was separated from the Middle Shajara reservoir by yellow green mudstone as revealed in Figure 1. It is defined by three samples so called SJ11, SJ12, SJ13 as explained in Table 1. Their positive slopes of the first procedure and negative slopes of the second procedure are displayed in Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11 and Table 1. Moreover, their flow rate fractal dimension and capillary pressure fractal dimension are also higher than those of sample SJ3 and SJ4 from the Lower Shajara Reservoir due to an increase in their permeability as clarified in (Table 1).

Figure 6: $\text{Log} (Q^{0.25}/Q_{\text{max}}^{0.25})$ & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ7.

Figure 9: $\text{Log} (Q^{0.25}/Q_{\text{max}}^{0.25})$ & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ11.

Figure 7: $\text{Log} (Q^{0.25}/Q_{\text{max}}^{0.25})$ & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ8.

Figure 11: $\text{Log} (Q^{0.25}/Q_{\text{max}}^{0.25})$ & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ13.

Figure 10: $\text{Log} (Q^{0.25}/Q_{\text{max}}^{0.25})$ & log pc versus log Sw for sample SJ12.

Overall a plot of number of flow rate dimension versus capillary pressure fractal dimension as shown in Figure 12 reveals three permeable zones of varying Petrophysical properties. Such variation in fractal dimension can account for heterogeneity which is a key parameter in reservoir quality assessment. This reservoir heterogeneity was also confirmed by plotting positive slope of the first procedure versus negative slope of the second procedure as described in (Figure 13).

Figure 12: Flow rate fractal dimension versus capillary pressure fractal dimension.

Figure 13: Slope of the first procedure versus slope of the second procedure.

Conclusion

- The sandstones of the Shajara Reservoirs of the Shajara formation permo-Carboniferous were divided here into three units based on flow rate fractal dimension.
- The Units from base to top are: Lower Shajara flow rate Fractal dimension Unit, Middle Shajara flow rate Fractal Dimension Unit, and Upper Shajara flow rate Fractal Dimension Unit.
- These units were also proved by capillary pressure fractal dimension.
- The fractal dimension was found to increase with increasing grain size and permeability.

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